

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL 3-D DELAMINATION BEHAVIOUR OF AN ANISOTROPIC LAYERED PLATE UNDER COMPRESSION LOADING

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Abstract

The failure mechanics of the so-called "delamination buckling" is investigated theoretically as well as experimentally considering laminated plate strips made of carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy. The laminates contain one through-width delamination between two adjacent plies, which separates them into two sublaminates. The deformation behaviour caused by the in-plane compressive loading is characterized by the buckling of the two sublaminates, which results in large out-of-plane displacements. The theoretical study is based on a three-dimensional finite element model. Results of a geometrically non-linear analysis covering pre- and post-buckling as well as fracture mechanics are presented. To illustrate the structural behaviour, a three-dimensional displacement plots for an axial displacement is shown.

In order to predict crack growth the energy release rates for mode I,II and mode III are determined using the virtual crack closure method. The dependence of G_I and G_{II} across the width of the specimen for different load levels is shown.

The results of the finite element analyses are compared with experimental data from compression tests, which were performed with plate strips containing artificial delaminations. The laser Moiré interferometry is used to get the three-dimensional displacement field and the crack front shape of the loaded specimen.

Keywords: delamination, local buckling, three-dimensional, Moiré interferometry, finite element calculation, energy release rate, mode I, mode II, mixed mode

1 Introduction

Among all damage types in fiber reinforced composites the delaminations are the most severe ones since they lead to a considerable strength reduction, especially if the structure is subjected to in-plane compressive loading. In this case the failure process is mostly initiated by the local buckling of the separated plies and the subsequent delamination growth caused by the high interlaminar stresses acting at the delamination crack front. In order to gain more insight into this failure process the behaviour of a simple configuration has been studied theoretically as well as experimentally. For this purpose the complete three-dimensional structure is investigated.

1.1 Geometry, Stacking Sequence, and Material

A schematic sketch of the configuration considered in this study is shown in figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Investigated configuration with dimensions in mm.

The investigated section of the plate strip has a total length of $x_{total} = 26$ mm and consists of a laminate with the following stacking sequence: $[0_2^{\circ} / +45^{\circ} / 0_2^{\circ} / -45^{\circ} / 0^{\circ} / 90^{\circ}]_{symm}$. Each of the 16 plies has a thickness of 0.125 mm, which gives a total thickness of 2 mm. The delamination is located in the middle of the laminate's length and spreads over the whole width of the strip, which is 20 mm. In the thickness direction the delamination is placed between the second and third ply. The composite material used in this study is a carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy called G30-500/5208. Each individual layer of the investigated laminate is assumed to be transversely isotropic. As material properties the following values have been used : $E_{11} = 140$ GPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 9$ GPa, $G_{12} = G_{13} = G_{23} = 5.9$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.3$.

2 Finite Element Analysis

The finite element method is used to model the behaviour of the investigated composite strips. In the present study the general purpose finite element program LARSTRAN has been employed. Because of the large displacements due to the buckling of the laminate, geometric nonlinearity has to be taken into account.

2.1 FE model

As already mentioned the three-dimensional problem has been modeled with a three-dimensional finite element model using 20-noded and 15-noded isoparametric elements. A typical finite element mesh is shown in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Typical finite element mesh.

Because of the expected unsymmetrical delamination behaviour the total length of the specimen has been considered. In order to reduce the degrees of freedom of the total model equivalent homogenized elastic properties for different layer groups are calculated according to the method described in [2]. The upper two 0° -plies were combined in one element layer which has the same stiffness. The thick lower sublaminat has been subdivided in two layers with two different stiffnesses. The first three plies ($+45^\circ/0_2^\circ$) were homogenized to one stiffness and the following 11 plies ($-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/0_2^\circ/+45^\circ/0_2^\circ$) were also homogenized to one stiffness. Only the thin upper sublaminat has the pure orthotropic property. In the region close to the crack tip the mesh is refined, according to a convergence study, in order to gain precise values of nodal forces and displacements, which are used as input data for the energy release rate calculations. On one side of the specimen the constraints $u = 0$ have been imposed. On the other the strip is loaded by prescribed displacements. The type of boundary condition is clamped, according to the experimental set-up. Imperfections of the structure, which are caused by the inserted release film, are taken into account by prescribing initial transverse displacements. The shape of this initial deformation is described by a sinusoidal wave with the amplitude w_0 which has been imposed on the thin sublaminat only.

2.2 Fracture Mechanics

For the investigated configuration the crack opening displacement is generally of a mixed-mode type. This means that the total energy release rate G_{total} for the three-dimensional case is the sum of the mode I, II and mode III component ($G_{total} = G_I + G_{II} + G_{III}$).

Since the total critical energy release rate $G_{total,c}$ for interlaminar fracture in the considered material is not a constant, G_{total} has to be separated into its mode I,II and mode III component. Then some appropriate failure criterion based on mixed-mode interlaminar fracture toughness measurements can be applied. The strain energy release rates for mode I, II and mode III are calculated according to the virtual crack closure technique [1], which is based on the nodal results of five forces and five displacement just ahead and behind the crack tip.

3 Results from the FE Analyses

In the presented example the delamination is located between the second and third ply, which means that the delaminated layer has a thickness of 0.25 mm. An initial, unsymmetrical imperfection with an amplitude of $w_0 = 0.012$ mm is assumed. Since the thin sublaminat's bending stiffness is low compared to the thick one's and its axial stiffness is relatively high in comparison to that of the thick sublaminat it could be anticipated that the transverse deflection of the

Figure 3.3: Three-dimensional deformed geometry of the total specimen under a prescribed axial load $u = 0.08$ mm.

Figure 3.4: Energy release rate G_I versus the specimen width for different load levels.

thin sublaminates will occur at rather small loads. It could be ascertained that right from the beginning of loading the thin sublaminates began to deflect. A plot of the three-dimensional displacements of the whole specimen can be seen in figure 3.3.

The specimen was loaded step by step with an incremental axial displacement of 0.02 mm. The inner part of the specimen starts to separate immediately. For the first three load steps a penetration of the two free edges of the delaminating sublaminates could be noticed. After the fourth load step the two sublaminates start to separate as the inner part of the delaminated sublaminates did right from the beginning. The displacement values a few element widths away from the free edge were for all load steps much higher than in the penetration zone. Even when the model was loaded beyond the stress level at which crack growth could be observed in the experiment ($\sigma_D = 220$ MPa) no large out of delamination plane deflection could be noticed along the free edges.

In order to estimate the onset of delamination growth the energy release rates G_I and G_{II} are plotted versus the width of the specimen for various load steps. The mode III values had been very low so that they could be neglected. Figure 3.4 shows a plot of the mode I component and figure 3.5 shows a plot of the mode II component for different load steps (prescribed axial

Figure 3.5: Energy release rate G_{II} versus the specimen width for different load levels.

Figure 3.6: Energy release rates G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} along the centerline of the specimen versus prescribed axial displacements u .

displacements u). The plots of figure 3.4 and 3.5 demonstrate, what has already been mentioned, namely that the crack opening displacement is in general a superposition of mode I, II and mode III. Since G_I , G_{II} and G_{III} do not increase equally with loading the ratio $G_I/G_{II}/G_{III}$ is not a constant as demonstrated in figure 3.6. The steep drop of the G_I value at the edge of the specimen see figure 3.6 represents a crack closure, which happens when a prescribed value of $u = 0.2$ was applied.

4 Specimen Fabrication and Test Procedure

Composite panels were laminated from unidirectional prepreg tapes and cured in an autoclave according to the supplier's recommendation. The delamination was achieved by inserting a 0.012 mm thick and 8 mm wide TEFLON FEP fluorocarbon film between the second and third ply. Glass/epoxy loading tabs were bonded onto each end of the plates using room temperature curing epoxy adhesive.

Figure 4.7: Specimen with dimensions in mm.

A typical specimen is shown in figure 4.7. The transverse displacements of the total specimen were recorded using the laser Moiré interferometry. The detailed description of this method was published in [5].

The out-of-plane displacement field of the deformed specimen has been recorded at several stress levels.

5 Test Results

The experimental data were obtained by testing four specimens. Stable crack propagation was observed in all experiments.

Figure 5.8 shows a typical plot of displacements for four different load levels. The dark-grey regions represent small deflections. The light-grey region is the larger are the out-of-plane deflections. The onset of a delamination starts always from one of the free edges and moves from there to the inner part of the specimen.

6 Discussion

Comparing the finite element results with the experimental results show a strong difference in the global behaviour of the specimen. In the experimental case the delamination starts from the free edges of the specimen. That means that the critical energy release rate is there earlier reached than in the inner part of the specimen. The finite element results show the contrary.

Figure 5.8: Out-of-plane displacement fields for the total specimen at different load levels.

The highest G_I and G_{II} values are calculated in the inner part of the specimen and at the free edges very low values are found. The delamination onset would be predicted at the inner part. The G_{III} values are very small, so the mode III case is neglected.

In the experiments the critical stress at which delamination occurs is $\sigma = 220$ MPa. From figure 3.4 and 3.5 it can be seen that $G_I = 105 \text{ J/m}^2$ and $G_{II} = 130 \text{ J/m}^2$ at $u = 0.08$ mm. This means that in the considered case delamination growth is governed by mixed mode crack opening. A common simple assumption for a mixed mode fracture criterium is $\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}} = 1$. In another study [3] $G_{Ic} = 160 \text{ J/m}^2$, $G_{IIc} = 520 \text{ J/m}^2$ has been evaluated for the here considered material. Using these values and the fracture criterium the delamination starts when an axial displacement of $u = 0.083$ mm is applied. That leads to failure stress of $\sigma_D = 300$ MPa.

7 Conclusions

The global specimen behaviour shows a strong difference between the experimental and the numerical results. The experiments yield that the delamination starts from the free edges of the specimen. In the finite element calculation a crack closure is observed near the free edges. The reason for the differences might be the penetration of the free edges right from the beginning. The natural behaviour is disturbed because of the lack of the contact zone, which might influence strongly the three-dimensional motion behaviour of upper and lower sublaminates.

The stress level calculated for the onset of the delamination is higher than the measured one. To get better agreement between the experimental and numerical results the penetration of the two sublaminates has to be prevented. The contact problem has to be taken in account.

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